

M0_Unconstrained-DEC on *Bicyclus*
 ancstates: global optim, 7 areas max. d=0.0281; e=0; j=0; LnL=-390.53

M0_Unconstrained-DEC on Bicyclus
 ancstates: global optim, 7 areas max. d=0.0281; e=0; j=0; LnL=-390.53

25 20 15 10 5 0
 Millions of years ago

M1_Constrained_a prior-DEC on Bicyclus
 ancstates: global optim, 7 areas max. d=0.035; e=0; j=0; LnL=-370.76

25 20 15 10 5 0
 Millions of years ago

M1_Constrained_a priori-DEC on *Bicyclus*
 ancstates: global optim, 7 areas max. d=0.035; e=0; j=0; LnL=-370.76

25 20 15 10 5 0
 Millions of years ago

M2_Constrained_Estimated Scalar-DEC on *Bicyclus*
 ancstates: global optim, 7 areas max. d=0.0615; e=0; j=0; LnL=-340.51

25 20 15 10 5 0
 Millions of years ago

M2_Constrained_Estimated Scalar-DEC on *Bicyclus*
 ancstates: global optim, 7 areas max. d=0.0615; e=0; j=0; LnL=-340.51

25

20

15

10

5

0

Millions of years ago